

Systematic Grouping of Residuals in RNN and CNN From Eye Movement Behaviour Patterns

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Abstract

In most cases, graphs are a natural way of representing every kind of data, often nature is referred to as the inherent characteristics and quality of physical phenomena; the natural way for its representation is through a graph. The relationship between human interactions, animals and soil can be represented and depicted as a graph. Also, the most paradigmatic case is that knowledge is presented as a graph and as a form of ontology in relationships and hierarchies among the concepts and words. However, while a long list and sets of data may represent events that can be classified by order or category, graphs that include relationship characteristics allow for a schematic presentation that includes different types of relationship categories. This is the natural assembly, of different types of human behaviour patterns. In this paper, we present human eye movement behaviour patterns in search mode while they are involved in a certain activity like surfing the web. The residual from the data collected is represented in a natural structure in the form of a stalactite plot of residuals from Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) classification. The residual fit shows that CNN has the highest rate in terms of True positive cases of eye movement behaviour compared to RNN.

Keywords: Natural Assemble, Schematic dataset, Convolutional Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network, Residual output, Performance rate

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1 INTRODUCTION

As one of the powerful models in structural data classification is in Deep Learning, such as the CNN and RNN which allows for the determination of natural structure in the form of atomic coordinates for all attributes related to a particular dataset. Data such as user behaviour data like fixations on visual interface continue to be a primary

source of mechanistic knowledge of physiological and cognitive perceptive attributes of users, the implications of such data extend from basic research to translational studies and rationale behind the design and nature of the data. Reflecting on some of the importance of the technique, the number of published works in behavioural user data structures has rapidly grown to more than 1000 within numerous research areas with structural data analysis.

To support the need for an increasing structural representation in data on user behavioural scenarios, a set of network structures in data based on the residual plot with baseline estimates has been established in this work and made available to researchers in the field of data science and data structures.

While the need for data collection methods has been increasingly rationalized, deployment of data integrity and management to archived datasets relating to human behaviour has been slow and uncertain. Hence the need to represent these data in an assembled manner for vivid understanding and user assessment has gone to its advanced level. This paper presents a formal method of data representation in residual form rather than the standardised form of data presentation.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Today, almost every research area relies on numbers, figures, and data, a lot of data is considered and investigated through visualisation, and decisions are made through this initial stage [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Sometimes, it is not always easy to understand the complexity of the data presented in front of us for evaluation purposes and certain issues such as data presentation may prove to be bogus [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. The brain may have some form of comprehension of data it could also be quite cumbersome to assume or make anything significant value it.

Data presentation is the change of rudimentary information into numeric delineations that tell a story [11, 12]. Choosing what data to share and how to share it is the principle of decision-making in data visualisation. Data visualisation and analysis can take numerous structures, so as a rule the perceptions presented in diagrams outline the structure and different types of mathematical clarifications that define it. Information presentation does not just end at data visualisation, there are also logic flows, pocket diagrams, and guides that are additional sorting for information perception [13, 14, 15, 16]. Every time we are introduced to the logic behind a concept in nations featured for accentuation we are given an eclipse about the information representation.

The utilization of intelligent analytics is used as an elevated kind of information presentation for standalone purposes and other uses, this gives an insight into the utilisation of channels in the standard representation of data [17, 18, 19, 20]. Structural assemblies are very important in information representation which gives a message or a story behind its information perception, this is a basic apparatus for every field of research. Information perception is very fundamental in strategizing the key data presentation and dynamic analysis of the presented data.

One of the main advantages of structural data analysis is that it tackles the difficulty of placing the information in perspectives to diagrammatical structure in

addition to the adjustment of information for investigating openings and patterns. Its disadvantage is that it gives an assessment and not the exactness of behaviour patterns; and is also one-sided in the human interface for the case of perception [21, 22, 23]. The papers look at natural assemblies in behaviour data generated from online behaviour analysis of users to two different webpages and a standard structure was obtained from the residual output with CNN and RNN, the performance for both methods in the resultant vector matrix was produced from the generated data which was accessed using the receiver operating characteristics curve (ROC) curve.

3 METHOD

Data was captured from an online survey with 100 random participants who were willing to take part on different webpages, which resulted in a collection of image sequences (10,000) of less than 10 minutes of interaction. This is done through an online mobile application with an eye-tracking embedded app (Gaze recorder), a real-time face and eye tracker with little hardware specification. It has high accuracy and precision based on integrated cameras independent of the device. The users' eye color and movement including pupil dilation and constriction were recorded. Each participant faces the camera lens with an upright position of the head and interacts with two different webpages (E-learning websites ("zyro.com" and "www.ui.org")), by just surfing and online cataloging for a minimal time of 10 minutes. The mobile app captures their eye movement behaviour patterns and touch screen fixations to record pupil dilation which is termed as "stress" and constriction, termed as "relaxed". Though behaviour is a complex concept. The method's scope is based on these two basic forms of human emotion.

The dataset generated contains these basic forms of user attributes with aggregates of seven instances used for residual and stalactite plots called the natural assemblies of data derived from the list of user behavioural activities. The residuals were computed from the resultant vector-matrix from CNN and RNN and analysis was based on the supervised method where the user response was grouped into "stressed" and "relaxed". These are discussed below.

3.1 Convolutional Neural Network

The Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet/CNN) takes an input image of the generated data matrix and assigns learnable bias (hidden layers) to various aspects in the image that differentiate one from the other. It requires pre-processing but at a lower rate as compared to other classification methods. CNN can learn and train the filter characteristics of a data model. Its architecture is analogous to that of the connectivity pattern of

Figure 1: Eye movement data captured from a mobile phone of participants.

neurons in the brain by an organization of the visual cortex. A typical CNN is usually more difficult to illustrate in detail because of its convolutional structure and a lot of additional layers such as the local contrast with normalised and batch normalised pooling layers, below (Figure 3) is a high-level illustration of a typical CNN, with input image layer $l = 0(CNN - 1)$, containing eye movement data, a convolutional layer, a non-linearity addition $l = 1(CNN - 2)$ and fully connected layer $l = 3(CNN - 3)$. CNNs usually need relatively little pre-processing as compared to other visual image classification algorithms.

This implies that the network always learns to optimize the kernels or filters through automated learning to produce residuals whereas in traditional algorithms these filters are hand-engineered. This independency of filters from prior knowledge and self-intervention in feature extraction is a major advantage for predictive accuracy. CNN is used in this paper for web-based and user behaviour datasets (web activities converted to visual text).

4 Recurrent neural networks

The Recurrent neural network (RNN) is where each node in each layer is connected in a form of a directed graph along a certain temporal sequence, they are meant to exhibit temporal dynamic behaviour. RNN can use their memory state to process variable-length sequences of inputs for the user data. RNN is used indiscriminately to two a kind broad class of network connectivity using a similar generalized structure, in this case, one of them is a finite impulse while the other is an infinite impulse. Each of these classes exhibits temporal physical dynamic behaviour. The finite impulse of recurring network structure is a form of a directed acyclic graph which can be unrolled and is replaced by a strict feed-forward network, the infinite impulse is a network structure that

forms a direct cyclic graph that can be unrolled. In both cases, the recurrent networks can have an additional set of stored states and this stored state can be under direct control by the neural network structure. Also, the storage can be replaced by another kind of network of a directed graph, if it incorporates latency or a feedback loop. This is referred to as gated memory. It is also part of a long short-term gated state with gated recurrent units which can also be a Feedback Neural Network. The structure above is used to generate another set of residual vectors from the behaviour data $x_1 \dots x_t$, as user attributes and hidden layers $H_1 \dots H_t$ (Figure 4) as the epochs between 1-10. The result from the residual output is discussed in the proceeding section.

5 RESULT

The stalactite plot in Figure 5 is a representation of the vector residuals from both CNN and RNN and correlates to the webpages the users interacted with. Each instance comes out as outlying on till the most significant point is detected and the pattern follows the same order till the end of the matrix. The two cognitive responses were predicted as 'stress' and 'relaxed' which represented dilation and constriction of the pupil of the eyes during an interaction. The most outlier instances detected for relaxed mood are the observations for "www.ui.org" websites and "zyro.com" websites recorded minimal stress movement i.e. pupils were less constriction in interaction with this website. Each residual point indicates the performance score for that pattern search and the vector in the matrix has a residual score for the coordinate. The stalactite plot is based on a natural assembly of data or residual points which is discussed in [1], this searches for the best possible fit based on a set of input vector-matrix using a linear regression fit. The URL signifies the number of webpages used for the instances, since a webpage contains more than one page, the ID for each page takes the

(a) Eye movement patterns from pupil dilation and constriction on *ui.com* website.

(b) Eye movement patterns from pupil dilation and constriction on *zyro.com* website

Figure 2: Website interfaces used for the user interaction

name of the page and data is arranged in a systematic order.

The error bar in Figure 6 presents the residuals from RNN and CNN of free viewing on eye movement behaviour recordings that contain an aggregate of the total instances used produced for the generated data, this includes fixation locations on the webpages from the two categories of cognitive response. The residuals harmonize the residual data and represent the vector predicted output from these two categories, stress, and relaxation

of the eye movement pattern. A free eye movement was recorded and mapped to the window size of the stimuli, and hence the length of the residual output is the same as the length of the dataset. The size and variability of the behaviour data within the dataset present a robust form of evaluating and comparing the computation model used in presenting them and also a thorough way of quantifying strategies of the behaviour data. The stalactite is a good way of observing the starting of the dataset and determining whether viewing strategies can change the tolerance of the categorised vector matrix. The figure shows that a minimal change is needed to optimise the process between CNN and RNN in residual output.

The receiver operating characteristics (ROC)(Figure 7) show that CNN has the highest performance rate for both models and the learning process is consistent, unlike the RNN. The performance is above 0.8% and close to 0.98% with a minimal error of 0.02%. The instances in residual output are closely matched to the initial response of the participants while interacting online and online experience can be in a close loop and quite similar emotional responses can be observed in most of the participants from the pupil changes. The computation model from the pupil is derived from the model's parameter, which calculates the change in the area of dilation and constriction from the eye movement that causes the fixation points on the visual interface.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper set out to investigate natural assemblies in residuals produced by recurrent neural networks and convolutional neural networks in eye behaviour patterns from a dataset of eye movement behaviour patterns. The residual output from the CNN and RNN was used as the input matrix for the natural assembly of the data. In this case, instead of using the dataset as an input matrix for the natural assembly, the vector residuals produced by both models are used to plot the natural structure of the data in the form of a stalactite plot. The performance in residual output is calculated and CNN has the highest performance. Future work would be to use the residual data as a form of input matrix to predict another set of response data and demonstrate another high-level model of data presentation in a simplified and decoded form.

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Figure 3: CNN for different eye movements and eye color attributes to different websites.

Figure 4: RNN model for data and residual generatio.

Figure 5: Residual plot for CNN and RNN on eye and color behaviour data from online interaction using natural assembles.

Figure 6: Error plot for the residuals from the behaviour dataset on CNN and RNN.

Figure 7: ROC for CNN and RNN in residual computation for behaviour data.

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